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C-CELL HYPERPLASIA DISEASED THYROID

"I SEE A SEA FULL OF C'S"

MULTIPLY 2

Create a C-Cell token Medi (1 health, 1 attack damage).

This ability can be performed up to 2 times a turn.

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FOLLICULAR CELL HEALTH THYROID

"PUMPING OUT HORMONES 3 TO 5 AT A TIME"

ENERGY BOOST

Once per turn, a Medi you control has its ability costs reduced by 1 ATP until your next turn.

HORMONAL STRIKE 3

You may spend 1 ATP. If you do, increase this attack's damage to 4 this turn.

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THYROID HEALTH THYROID

"KEEPING YOUR ENGINE RUNNING SMOOTHLY"

THYROID STORM 6 1²

Attacks/abilities of all your Medis cost 0 ATP this turn. Add a sleep token to any Medi that performs an action while affected by this ability.

METABOLIC OVERDRIVE 2+

+X damage (X = # of Medis you control).

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PARAFOLLICULAR C-CELL HEALTH THYROID

"THERE IS JUST TOO MUCH MILK IN HERE"

STRONG BONES 1

When attacking, this Medi does not take damage.

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HASHIMOTO DISEASE DISEASED THYROID

"IS IT NAP TIME YET"

SLEEPY 2

Add a sleep token to any Medi. This ability can be performed up to 2 times a turn.

BULL-DOZER 3+

+X damage (X = # of Medis with sleep tokens).

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GRAVES DISEASE DISEASED THYROID

"OVERCLOCKING YOUR METABOLISM"

HYPERACTIVE

-1 ATP costs for attacks/abilities of all your Medis.

EARLY GRAVE 2+

+X damage (X = # of attacks and abilities you used this turn with reduced costs).

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ADRENAL MEDULLA HEALTHY ADRENAL

"LET'SSS FIGHT... OR MAYBE NOT"

FIGHT OR FLIGHT 2+

Role 1 die if an opponent blocks this Medi.
 1-2: Negate all damage.
 3-6: +2 damage dealt to blocking Medi.

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ADRENAL CORTEX HEALTHY ADRENAL

"SSSO MANY SSSTEROID HORMONESSS"

STRESS MANAGMENT

Once per turn, change any die result by +1 or -1.

ALDOSTER-STONE 3+

Roll 1 die as this Medi attacks.
 1-2: Deal 1 damage to a Medi you control.
 3-6: Deal 2 damage to any target.

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ADRENAL GLAND HEALTHY ADRENAL

"SSSALTY, SSSWEET, SSSTEROIDS"

PUMPED UP 2+

Choose a Medi you control. Roll a die.
 1-2: Add 1 Fatigue token.
 3-6: Add 2 Strengthen tokens.

PURE ADRENALINE 5+

Roll a die. Attack again unless a 1 or 2 is rolled.

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DBH DEFICIENCY DISEASED ADRENAL

"NO PRESSURE, NO PRESSURE AT ALL"

LOW PRESSURE

Once per turn, if an opponent attempts to block a Medi you control, you may have them roll a die.
 1-4: Opponent Medi fails to block.
 5-6: Opponent Medi blocks as normal.

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CUSHING SYNDROME DISEASED ADRENAL

"I SSSUCK YOUR ENERGY AND GIVE YOU MASSS"

EASY BRUISING

Once during your turn, 1 opponent rolls a die.
 1-4: Medis they control gain 1 Fragile token until end of turn.

HEFTY SLAM 4+

Roll a die as this Medi attacks. Deal damage to any Medi equal to half the result (rounded up).

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ADDISON DISEASE DISEASED ADRENAL

"I WASSS BORN IN THE DARK"

HORMONE REPLACEMENT THERAPY

Whenever any die would be rolled, two are rolled instead. You pick the result.

OVERCOME INSUFFICIENCY 2+

+X damage (X = # of dice showing 3+ this turn).

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ALPHA CELL HEALTHY PANCREAS

"LOW SUGAR? GIVE ME A CALL"

MAKE DONUTS
Exhaust Alpha Cell. Produce 1 ATP for the turn (just like an ATP card).

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BETA CELL HEALTHY PANCREAS

"WHEN SUGARS RISE, I WILL NORMALIZE"

RAKE IN THE SUGAR 2
Give a Medi you control 1 Strengthen token. Usable only once per turn.

INSULIN SPIKE 2
Also deal X damage to any opponent Medi (X = # of Medis you control with a Strengthen token).

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PANCREAS HEALTHY PANCREAS

"ON A QUEST TO DIGEST!"

MASTER OF CONSERVATION
All unused ATP for the turn is conserved for your next turn.

DRAIN THE RESERVES 3 X
Also deal X damage divided between ≤ 2 opponent Medis (X = ATP spent on this attack).

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TYPE II DIABETES DISEASED PANCREAS

"WHAT? HOW MANY DONUTS DID I EAT?"

URINARY TRACT INFECTION 1
Any Medi that blocks this attack takes +1 additional damage.

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TYPE I DIABETES DISEASED PANCREAS

"SUGAR, SUGAR EVERYWHERE BUT NOT A GRAIN TO USE"

VISION LOSS
Once per turn, choose a Medi you control. Opponents cannot target it with effects until your next turn.

LOTSA DONUTS 4
Also deal X damage to any Medi (X = # of unused ATPs they control). That Medi cannot use ATP during its next turn.

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PANCREATITIS DISEASED PANCREAS

"STOP EATING YOURSELF!"

AUTODIGEST X
When an opponent Medi dies, deal damage to a Medi equal to the number of Medis that have died this turn. Repeat up to X times this turn.

FLARE UP 4
Also deal 2 damage to a player. Give that player 1 Inflammation token.

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IGM ANTIBODY 0

"I LOVE TO GIVE COMPLEMENTZZZ"

SCRAMBLE FOR ANSWERS
Look at the top 5 cards of your deck and add 1 to your hand. Place the rest back on the top or bottom of your deck in any order you choose.

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IGG ANTIBODY 1

"I WILL FIND YOU AND I WILL ZZZTING YOU"

DEJA VU
Search through your deck for a card, then place it in your hand. Shuffle your deck.

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SHIELD ELECTRIC SYLVA FOREST 2

STAFF
1 Thyroid family (draw a card)

ELECTRIC JOLT
Once per turn, if staffed, -2 ATP cost of attacks/abilities for one of your Medis until the end of turn.

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THIRSTY'S HAUNTED MANSION SYLVA FOREST 2

STAFF
1 Adrenal family (draw a card)

GAMBLE IT ALL
Once per turn, if staffed, roll a die.
1-2: Discard your hand, then draw that many.
3-6: Discard any number, then draw that many.

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DIGESTUM AQUARIUM SYLVA FOREST 2

STAFF
1 Pancreas family (draw a card)

REST AND DIGEST
If staffed, you may add additional staff from any family. Each additional staff provides +1 ATP until the end of turn.

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THYROID REMOVAL TREATMENT SURGERY

0

CUT IT OUT ✓

Choose one:

1. Sacrifice 2 Medis you control. Destroy 1 opponent Medi.
2. Sacrifice 1 Medi you control from the Thyroid family. Destroy 1 opponent Medi.

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LEVOTHYROXINE TREATMENT HORMONE

0

ENERGY BOOST ✓

Choose one:

1. Reduce the cost of abilities/attacks of a Medi you control by 1 ATP until end of turn.
2. Reduce the cost of attacks/abilities of a Thyroid family Medi you control by 2 ATP until end of turn.

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METHIMAZOLE TREATMENT HORMONE

3

FROM BEYOND THE GRAVE X

During your turn, return a Medi from your discard pile to the battlefield. If it is from the Thyroid family, it may attack this turn.

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SEMAGLUTIDE TREATMENT METABOLISM

2

PROPER SUGAR MANAGEMENT ✓

ATP cards each produce 2 ATP until the end of turn. If you control a Medi from the Pancreas family, this effect lasts until your next turn.

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INSULIN TREATMENT METABOLISM

2

WHERE IT'S NEEDED X

During your turn, draw X cards. If you control a Medi from the Pancreas family, draw an additional card for free.

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PANCREATIC ENZYMES TREATMENT METABOLISM

3

PERFECTED DIGESTION ✓

Until the end of the turn, whenever any Medi dies, you gain 1 life and a Medi you control gains 1 health. If you control a Medi from the Pancreas family, this effect lasts until your next turn.

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DROXIDOPA

TREATMENT
CVS

1

PRESSURE SURGE

Each player rolls a die. The player(s) who rolls the highest number takes damage equal to the number they rolled.

If you control a Medi from the Adrenal family, you may reroll your die one time.

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MIFEPRISTONE

TREATMENT
HORMONE

2

NO WORRIES

Remove all negative tokens from 1 Medi you control. If you control a Medi from the Adrenal family, remove all negative tokens from all Medis you control.

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HYDROCORTISONE

TREATMENT
HORMONE

4

CORTICOID BOOST

During your turn, roll three dice. Draw cards equal to the highest number you rolled. If you control a Medi from the Adrenal family, gain life equal to the lowest number you rolled as well.

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Inflammation: Take 1 damage per turn

Sleep: Cannot perform an action for 1 round of play

Fatigue: Decrease attack damage by -1

Strengthen: Increase attack damage by +1

Shield: Decrease damage done to this Medi by -1

Fragile: Increase damage done to this Medi by +1

Inflammation: Take 1 damage per turn

Sleep: Cannot perform an action for 1 round of play

Fatigue: Decrease attack damage by -1

Strengthen: Increase attack damage by +1

Shield: Decrease damage done to this Medi by -1

Fragile: Increase damage done to this Medi by +1

Inflammation: Take 1 damage per turn

Sleep: Cannot perform an action for 1 round of play

Fatigue: Decrease attack damage by -1

Strengthen: Increase attack damage by +1

Shield: Decrease damage done to this Medi by -1

Fragile: Increase damage done to this Medi by +1